

Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of some Substituted 1,3,4-Thiadiazolo[3,2-*a*]-*s*-triazin-5-phenyl-7-thiones and Imidazo-[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-ones

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2-Amino-5-aryl-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (1) have been refluxed with benzoyl isothiocyanate to get *N*-[5-aryl-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]-*N*-benzoyl thioureas (1a). These on refluxing with PCl_5 and POCl_3 give 2-aryl-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-*a*]-*s*-triazin-5-phenyl-7-thiones (3). Compound 1 on refluxing with chloroacetic acid and anhydrous sodium acetate gives 2-substituted-aryl-imidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-ones (2). The compounds have been screened for antifungal activities.

In continuation of our interest in the five- and six-membered heterocycles containing nitrogen and sulphur atoms such as 1,3,4-thiadiazoles, *s*-triazine and imidazole derivatives possessing promising biological activities¹, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise bridgehead nitrogen heterocycles containing the above mentioned rings like 1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-*a*]-*s*-triazin-5-phenyl-7-thione and imidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-one (Table 1).

These compounds were screened for antifungal activity against *H. oxyzae* and *A. flavous* by adopting inhibition zone technique². The results (Table 1) reveal that compounds 3 are found more effective against *A. flavous* as compared to *H. oxyzae* and compound 2 more effective against *A. flavous* as compared to *H. oxyzae*. Compounds 3b, 3c, 3c' showed greater activities against both the fungi as compared to the rest of the compounds in the series 2a,

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL AND ANTIFUNGAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3*

Compd no.	M.p. °C	ν_{max} cm^{-1}	δ	Zone of inhibition, mm(%)	
				<i>H. oxyzae</i> mg/ml	<i>A. flavours</i> mg/ml
2a	140	2 970, 1 740, 1 610, 1 600, 1 280, 1200, 1 080, 800, 660	1.0 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 2.6 (2H, q, benzylic), 3.95 (6H, s, 2 $\cdot \text{OCH}_3$), 4.21 (2H, s, CH_2 at C_6), 6.45, 7.75 (H, s, ArH)	13 (53.8)	13 (53.8)
a'	158	3 000, 1 750, 1 620, 1 590, 1 770, 1 030, 820, 650	1.10 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.25–1.27 (6H, t, 2 OCH_2CH_3), 2.5 (2H, q, benzylic), 3.95–4.3 (4H, m, 2 $\times \text{OCH}_2$), 4.2 (2H, CH at C_6), 6.4 (H, s, ArH), 7.18 (H, s, ArH)	11 (45.4)	18 (66.6)
b	180	3 000, 1 760, 1 610, 1 580, 1 240, 1 120, 1 020, 840, 720	1.00 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.4 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.5 (2H, t, benzylic), 3.9 (6H, s, 2 $\cdot \text{OCH}_3$), 4.2 (2H, s, CH_2 at C_6), 6.98 (H, s, ArH), 7.3 (H, s, ArH)	13 (53.8)	17 (64.7)
b'	198	2 980, 1 720, 1 610, 1 580, 1 280, 1 200, 1 075, 810, 650	1.10 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.4 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.53 (2H, t, benzylic), 4.0–4.38 (4H, m, 2 OCH_2), 4.2 (2H, CH_2 at C_6), 6.8 (H, s, ArH), 7.2 (H, s, ArH)	18 (66.6)	2.1 (71.4)
c	148	2 990, 1 725, 1 610, 1 600, 1 200, 1 190, 1 010, 850, 720, 600	1.0 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.2–1.4 (4H, m, CH_2CH_3), 2.3 (2H, t, benzylic), 3.8 (6H, s, 2 OCH_3), 4.0 (2H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-CH}_2$), 6.7 (H, s, ArH), 7.2 (H, s, ArH)	8 (25)	9 (33.3)

c'	180	2 970, 1 720, 1 610, 1 600, 1 220, 1 170, 1 120, 870, 750, 650	1.10 (3H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.24 (4H, t, CH_2CH_2), 1.51 (6H, t, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 2.62 (2H, t, benzylic), 4.1 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}_6$), 6.62 (H, s, ArH), 7.2 (H, s, ArH)	15 (25)	16 (62.6)
d	198	3 000, 1 750, 1 610, 1 600, 1 540, 1 270, 1 200, 1180, 1 110, 820, 720, 650	1.2 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 2.5 (2H, q, benzylic), 3.87 (2H, m, OCH_2), 4.3 (3H, m, OCH_3 and 2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$ at C_6) 4.1 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.6 (H, s, ArH), 7.2 (H, s, ArH)	12 (50)	13 (53.8)
e	188	3 000, 1 750, 1 650, 1 600, 1 540, 1 260, 1 200, 1 180, 800, 720, 650	1.10–1.20 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 2.43 (2H, q, benzylic), 3.9 (2H, s, OCH_2CH_3), 4.2 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.4 (2H, s, CH_2 at C_6), 6.53 (H, s, ArH), 7.2 (H, s, ArH)	10 (40)	16 (62.6)
3a	158	3 000, 1 625, 1 600, 1 230, 1 190, 1 010, 820, 620	1.15 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 2.6 (2H, q, benzylic), 4.2 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.8–7.4 (7H, s, ArH)	14 (57.1)	12 (50)
a'	183	2 900, 1 620, 1 600, 1 230, 1 180, 1 020, 840, 620	1.12 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.5–1.6 (6H, t, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.8–3 (2H, q, benzylic), 4.6 (4H, q, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 6.1–6.3 (1H, s, ArH), 7.1–7.3 (1H, s, ArH), 7.6–7.95 (5H, s, ArH)	12 (50)	13.9 (56.8)
b	188	3 000, 1 640, 1 590, 1200, 1180, 1010, 820, 710, 620	1.12–1.25 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.52–1.65 (2H, m, CH_2CH_2), 2.9 (2H, q, benzylic), 4.2 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.95 (H, s, ArH), 7.3 (H, s, ArH), 7.8–7.85 (5H, m, ArH)	13 (53.8)	18 (66.6)
b'	210	2 900, 1 640, 1 600, 1 210, 1 190, 1 020, 1020, 840, 710	0.96 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.30–1.50 (6H, m, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$, and 2H, m, CH_2CH_3), 2.6 (2H, t, benzylic), 4.2 (4H, q, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 6.8 (H, s, ArH), 7.2 (H, s, ArH), 7.8 (5H, s, ArH)	12 (50)	15 (60)
c	198	2 900, 1 640, 1 620, 1 210, 1 190, 1 010, 800, 720	0.95 (3H, t, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.2–1.3 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2 , and 4H, m, CHCH) 2.8 (2H, q, benzylic), 4.2 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.5 (H, s, ArH), 7.1 (H, s, ArH), 7.4 (5H, s, ArH)	14 (57.1)	20 (70)

Table-1 (contd)

c	148	2 900, 1 650, 1 600, 1 210, 1 110, 810, 650	1.1-1.3 (3H, m, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.2-1.3 (4H, m, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.5-1.6 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.6 (2H, t, benzylic), 4.15-4.32 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.5 (H, s, ArH), 7.25 (H, s, ArH), 7.40 (5H, m, ArH)	17 (64.7)	19 (68.4)
d	186	3 000, 1 670, 1 610, 1 220, 1 150, 810, 650	1-1.35 (3H, t, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.26-1.35 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.6 (2H, q, benzylic), 4.2 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.4 (2H, q, CH ₂ CH ₃), 6.8-6.9 (H, s, ArH), 7.25-7.5 (5H, m, ArH)	15 (60)	12 (50)
e	188	3 000, 1 650, 1 620, 1 280, 1 170, 1 100, 820, 650	1.20 (3H, t, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.6-1.8 (3H, t, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.6 (2H, q, benzylic), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.2 (2H, q, CH ₂ CH ₃), 6.8-6.9 (H, s, ArH), 7.0-7.1 (ArH), 7.25-7.5 (5H, m, ArH)	16 (62.1)	13 (53.8)

- a : Q = 2,4-dimethoxy-5-ethylphenyl
 a' : Q = 2,4-diethoxy-5-ethylphenyl
 b : Q = 2,4-dimethoxy-5-n-propylphenyl
 b' : Q = 2,4-diethoxy-5-n-propylphenyl
 c : Q = 2,4-dimethoxy-5-n-butylphenyl
 c' : Q = 2,4-diethoxy-5-n-butylphenyl
 d : Q = 2-methoxy-4-ethoxy-5-ethylphenyl
 d' : Q = 2-ethoxy-4-ethoxy-5-ethylphenyl

2b, 3b', 2c' and 2d' were found more active against both the fungi as compared to other compounds.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) in 60 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Elemental analysis was recorded on a Heraeus analyser, and C, H and N analyses of the compounds were found satisfactory.

2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes were converted into their corresponding thiosemicarbazones and then cyclised by alkaline K₃Fe(CN)₆ in alcohol to give 2-amino-5-aryl-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (1).

N-[5-(2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]-N-benzoylthiourea (1a) : Compound 1 (0.01 mol) was refluxed with benzoyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in acetone for 2 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol.

2-(2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-a]-s-triazin-5-phenyl-7-thione (3) : A mixture of 1a (0.01 mol), PCl₅ (0.11 mol) and POCl₃ (15 ml) was refluxed for 2 h and then crushed ice added to it. The solid thus obtained was crystallised from methanol.

2-(2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylphenyl)imidazo[2,1-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-one (2) : Compound 1 (0.01 mol) was refluxed with chloroacetic acid (0.02 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate in dry methanol for 8-10 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

References

- R. M. ABDUL REHMAN, E. L. GENDY and M. B. MAHMOUD, *Indian J. Chem., Sect B*, 1990, **29**, 352; H. ODA, Y. MASAKI and H. NAGASHIMA, *Chem Abstr.* 1988, **108**, 131762; F. F. ABDEL LATIF R. M. SHABER and S. A. MAHGUAB, *J Heterocycl Chem.* 1989, **26**, 769; L. C. MARCH, G. S. BAJWA and M. M. JOULIE, *J Med Chem.* 1976 **19**, 845; C. K. JOSHI, V. PAIHAH and V. GARRY, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 1074; J. W. RIPPON "Medical Mycology". Saunders, Philadelphia, 1974, p. 534; C. S. ANDOTRA, T. C. LANGER, S. DHAM and P. KAUR, *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 1993, **55**; *J Nep Chem Soc.* 1992, **11**, 15.
- M. PROPIVA, *Chemie, Antihistaminovick taketa, Histaminove Skuping Ceskoslovensker. Akedemie, Vcd. Praka*, 1955.